

Psychological Impact of Covid-19 Described With SWOT Analysis

Md Swaid Sameh, Farhana Binta Fozal, Tanvir Hasan Shuvo, Mir Jerine Farhath &
Tanzim Hossain Oyshi

Abstract

The Corona epidemic lasted for about two years. Its subsequent waves are more frightening and damaging than the previous ones. Not only has the pandemic increased the chance of infection-related mortality, but it has also increased the psychological strain. Various psychological disorders and major mental health repercussions, such as stress, worry, sadness, frustration, and uncertainty, emerged gradually throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. And the students have suffered more from this mental problem. Due to their long absence from school and their detention at home, they have been exposed to a wide range of psychological problems, which has led many to choose suicide. Students' mental health problems are now regarded as a public health issue. The objective of this work was to conduct a comprehensive review of the psychological effect on students after pandemic and covid impact on the education system. Along with this, the online learning system and some psychological issues that may get found after COVID-19 have also been discussed. Finally, a swot analysis is given on what has been discussed as well as some significant psychological issues are also discussed here.

IJSB

Accepted 12 January 2022
Published 22 January 2022
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5889747

Keywords: *Psychology, Covid-19, Education, SWOT, Depression.*

About Author (s)

Md Swaid Sameh (corresponding author), Undergraduate Student, Department of Management, Govt. Bangla College, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Farhana Binta Fozal, Undergraduate Student, Department of Bachelor of Business Administration, North South University, Bangladesh.

Tanvir Hasan Shuvo, Undergraduate Student, Department of Accounting & Information System, Govt. Bangla College, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Mir Jerine Farhath, Undergraduate Student, Department of Management, Govt. Bangla College, University of Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Tanzim Hossain Oyshi, Undergraduate Candidate from Vashantek Govt. College, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

A cluster of typical pneumonia cases was discovered in Wuhan, China, in December 2019, which was later identified as Coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) by the World Health Organization (WHO) on 11 February 2020 (Anand et al., 2020). Then the Organization (WHO) proclaimed a public health emergency of international concern and a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (Jasarevic et al., 2020). The pandemic has produced more than 305 million illnesses and 5.48 million fatalities as of 9 January 2022, making it one of the deadliest in history (Wikipedia contributors, 2022). In fact, the Corona epidemic spread around the world in late December 2019 and early January 2020 (Kelland, 2020). It was so havoc that so far 5503923 people have died all over the world (Worldometer, 2022). The SARS-CoV-2 virus causes a highly infectious respiratory illness. SARS-CoV-2 is assumed to transmit from person to person by droplets emitted by infected people when they cough, sneeze, or talk (Patient Education Publications, n.d.). European countries have suffered the most (Stewart, 2021). The epidemic not only caused death but also caused a variety of physical and mental problems (Stuijzand et al., 2020). Everything has been locked down for a long time all over the world, so everyone has to stay indoors (Team MetroPlus, 2020). As a result, most people have a variety of mental problems (Panchal et al., 2021). Many have even committed suicide as a result (Thakur & Jain, 2020). Students have suffered the most from these mental problems (Writers, 2021). Despite the rapid development of technology and online education in this epidemic, the mental problems of students have been noticed (Browning et al., 2021). There is a big difference between studying at home and studying outside, if students study in different ways, they can remember it quickly and easily, but studying online is a monotonous method (UNC-Chapel Hill Learning Center, 2020). The mindset of the students is very sensitive and on top of that, the bad effects of the lockdown have severely damaged their mental health (Pietrabissa, 2020). Just as it is detrimental to their education, it will also have dire consequences for their future lives (Dorn et al., 2021). Even with such a modern online education system, their studies have not progressed as it is monotonous (Dhawan, 2020). The consequences have been so devastating that many have chosen to commit suicide for no apparent reason (Abi Zeid Daou et al., 2021). These psychological problems following the Corona epidemic have done a lot of damage to the education sector (Islam et al., 2020).

Figure 1: Suicide Rates All Over The World:-

College of Medicine - Tucson. (2020, April 11). *Suicide rates spike through COVID-19 pandemic* | The Department of Psychiatry, University of Arizona Health Sciences.

Although the Corona epidemic has now been brought under control, this mental problem has not yet been completely resolved (Bodrud-Doza et al., 2020). Apart from mental problems, being away from everyone for a long time has caused a lot of social damage (Mayo Clinic Staff, 2021). Also, since everything is online at the moment, students are addicted to online video games such as PUBG, Fortnite Battle Royale, Apex Legends, DOTA 2 and parents can't do anything (Gray & Richtel, 2021). The students are the future of the country but if they have mental problems then the development of the country will be hampered (Torous & Keshavan, 2020). Mental health diseases affect an estimated 25% of the world's population. But after the Corona epidemic, it has increased (Arusha & Biswas, 2020). This problem is especially noticeable in the countries of the European Union (World Health Organization, n.d.). In addition, its psychological problems have spread to North America in the aftermath of the Corona epidemic (Xiong et al., 2020). Although the education system improved a lot in the aftermath of the Corona epidemic, the students did not get many good results from these (Saavedra, 2022). Which is a threat to our future generations (Muthuprasad et al., 2021). The rate of suicide in this region is also increasing due to this stress or instability (Pirkis et al., 2021). This is a huge issue and cannot be discussed in detail. So we discussed the opportunities, strengths, weaknesses, threats and finally gave a SWOT analysis to understand the discussion easily and promptly.

2. Objectives, Methodology & Limitations:

We have discussed some psychological & online education-related sectors separately and finally included a swot analysis to understand the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats from all the discussions. The parts with which the paper is arranged & which are useful to easy to understand, are described below.

Psychological effects on a student after COVID-19	Negative upshots on students' psychological health	Being asocial MIGHT be a thing for late	Learning wasn't ensured for all	Mental health issues got raised	Distant Learning: Future of Education	Psychological issues that may get found after COVID-19	SWOT Analysis of Post-psychological Impacts of COVID-19
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Our research is totally based on secondary data. I selected secondary data because it is simple to explain even though it is analyzed and interpreted data that may be shared by another company or author after proper modification. Government reports, websites, newspapers, online blogs, journals, and research papers, among other sources, were used to compile the data, information, fact, and statistic. All of the information was gathered from them via the internet.

2. Psychological effects on a student after COVID-19:

COVID-19, a global disquietude, not only oppressed the present-day economic circumstances extending worldwide but also dntrodden the catholic education system, regardless of the region (Friedman et al., 2020). Due to an entire uninterrupted shift in the scheme, from in-person classes to online, many of the students brought them into play both in forward-looking ways and in antithetical ones as well. The ongoing process of learning is mostly demonstrated to be detrimental psychologically to students. It leaves both rational and emotional contradiction sentiments (Far Abid Hossain et al., 2021).

Figure 2: The relationship between different variables of the study:-

Source: Sang, X., Menhas, R., Saqib, Z. A., Mahmood, S., Weng, Y., Khurshid, S., Iqbal, W., & Shahzad, B. (2021). The Psychological Impacts of COVID-19 Home Confinement and Physical Activity: A Structural Equation Model Analysis.

3. Online Learning System:

3.1 Negative upshots on students' psychological health:

Pandemic firstly initiated the permanent shutdown of the school campuses and since March 2020 and over 1.2 billion students found themselves waiting for the updates of school reopening, not making any appearances physically at schools (Northenor, 2020). It crumbled up the education for 150 countries and affected over 1.6 billion students eventually (World Bank Group, 2021). In the aftermath, when sound health, being safe come into question, then going online seemed to be the best option to go for (KY Counseling Center, 2021).

Figure 3: Mental health care for students:-

Source: Duffy, A., Saunders, K. E. A., Malhi, G. S., Patten, S., Cipriani, A., McNevin, S. H., MacDonald, E., & Geddes, J. (2019). Mental health care for university students: a way forward? *The Lancet Psychiatry*,

In this epoch of distant learning, students are getting embellished with despondency almost entirely (Fidalgo et al., 2020). Students are precipitated with so much for instance- parental death from Covid-19, being in the middle of a rampant pandemic where every new day commences with debunking the constant upward scaling of positive COVID-19 cases and death rates (Spinelli et al., 2020). Additionally, where surviving happens to be the major issue, keeping oneself shielded turns out to be the foremost thing to perpetuate, remaining alive, above all, is open to question (Expert Group Meeting on Male Roles and M et al., 2000).

3.2 Being asocial MIGHT be a thing for later:

Though the online education sounded engrossing at its commencement yet students gradually seemed to lose their interest in it and yet another fear raised by the parents that, without social interaction for this long term, they are frightened that students are going to be asocial (Sharma, 2020). Here, even after one round year of school closure half of the world's students still find it to be inflexible to tackle with (UNESCO, 2021).

Figure 4: Mental Health Education for Social interaction:-

Source: Park, Y., & Nakamura, J. (n.d.). How can we incorporate mental health education into schools? Consider the 5 T's. | Student Behavior Blog. Studentbehaviorblog

3.3 Learning wasn't ensured for all:

Massive movement of online learning without training and insufficient bandwidth, and less preparation was never going to play it right (Li & Lalani, 2020). Another issue, as that online education has been facilitated onto the students abruptly without scrutinizing the predominant question about how many students possess their computer or device that can get themselves entrance to the provided online materials. According to OECD data, 95% of the students from developed countries like Switzerland, Norway, and Australia possess their computers for their education purpose while the percentage comes at 34% in Indonesia. The presence of this gap wildly happens to be in the US, where all the 15-year-olds from an affluent background have their computers and only 25% of the disadvantaged backgrounds do. However, to ensure

having applicable digital devices, countries like New South Wales, Australia, and many others provided equipment.

Figure 5: How Many People Interested in Online & Offline Class:-

Source: Bock, H. (2020, August 31). Community College Biotechnology Fall 2020 Teaching Plans. InnovATEBIO.

3.4 Mental health issues got raised:

When someone already has mental health concerns, online education may worsen them (KY Counseling Center, 2021). It can resonate with fatigue like- Zoom Fatigue: which refers to feelings of exhaustion after a long period of virtual classes. As the students, these days, can't remain themselves joining in extracurricular, interconnecting with their friends, and maintaining a regular life, it is going to be hard for them to cope up with the stretched anxiety and stress (Afrin, 2021).

Figure 6: Tackling the mental health impact of the COVID-19 crisis:-

Source: Scarpetta, S., Colombo, F., & Hewlett, E. (2021, May 12). Tackling the mental health impact of the COVID-19 crisis: An integrated, whole-of-society response. OECD.

Higher stress also brings heightened symptoms of Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD), which would also be one of the substances endeavoring to govern over (Thienemann, n. d.). Also, studies reveal that there is the presence of predictive symptoms of acute stress disorder instant after being in a quarantine period of 9 days, whereas at present detachment from close ones, not paying a visit to the nearest ones has been normalized (Brooks et al., 2020). This period also provides trauma-related mental health disorders, insomnia, irritability, low mood, extended mental stress, emotional exhaustion, and many more. There might be a high probability of post-traumatic stress and a dramatic shift in behavior towards others (Brooks et

al., 2020). Substantial enhancement in emotions like annoyance, frustration, guilt, loneliness, isolation is going to be habitual (Boursier et al., 2020).

3.5 Distant Learning: Future of Education:

Distant online education, however, is not that atrocious as it sounds. It is determined to be malleable, easily approachable, also customizable according to the base of preferences and necessities of the students (eLearning Inside, 2021). Students can take classes and broaden their knowledge anytime and from anywhere on any particular subject whichever may be advantageous for them. Yet, which should be questioned is its productiveness. Requiring a structured environment, online education materials are demonstrated to be more effective than traditional ones (Li & Lalani, 2020). The study reveals it requires 40-50% less time and energy to learn something than in conventional classrooms (Puri, 2018). This might be a crucial thing to consider as students learn in their stride while learning something fundamentally, or re-reading, or even in terms of skipping which shapes learning with pleasure. Additionally, diverse online learning platforms like- Udemy, Coursera, Skillshare, et cetera are there to shift the learning curve right, offering the introverted students their comfort zone and acquiring knowledge even better (Koksal, 2020). These affix some sort of optimistic attitude towards the never-ending defeatism. Which, anyway, makes it the future of education. Nevertheless, an "IF" exists (Crockett, n.d.). This side of positivity only happens if technology is used effectively (Patricia Aguilera-Hermida, 2020) and also the attitude they possess about it (Ali, 2020). Students' lack of confidence in technology usage may impact negatively (Bower, 2019). In conclusion, it is somehow determined that online learning's negativity is far greater than the positivity it leaves (Northenor, 2020).

Figure 7:- Meaning of Distance Learning – Different Models and Future Trends:-

Source: Thais, T. (2019, January 3). *Meaning of Distance Learning – Different Models and Future Trends*. My Love for Learning.

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3.6 Psychological issues that may get found after COVID-19:

COVID-19 disturbance originated disruption on 60% of the world's student population which increased gradually over time (Akat & Karatas, 2020). It affected humanity profoundly. As these online classes and online learning happen to be the future of the learning method, thus having much screen-time is going to be a burning issue to solve later as it can cause fatigue, stress, and all other issues of the current period (Singh, 2020). In the pandemic, students were of the worst level of mental health problems which, however, can be of the same as before the lockdown (Meda et al., 2021). After the epoch of COVID-19, shifting the learning curve to its utmost level may get some of the students or learners in a better mental place later than the others (Singh et al., 2020). Yet, it must be mentioned that for the upward learning curve through online materials students must be ensured with a good internet which is not questionable in the developing countries like the USA, UK, and many others whereas developing and under-developing countries facing electricity issues find it to be a bit luxurious (Zalat et al., 2021). Thus, effective learning has not been assured for many students of many countries. The trauma that was caused due to the pandemic and the issues of mental health is being cared for in some places yet it is happening slowly which lifts the monumental interrogation if mental health can ever be the same as before (Stone, 2021). Yet, it cannot be ignored that being less social and lacking cognitive engagement sense may bring the students perpetual negativities in their learning system (Bower, 2019).

Figure 8:- Global mental health

Source: IHME, Global Burden of Disease

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Source: Ritchie, H. (2018, May 16). Global mental health: five key insights which emerge from the data. Our World in Data. <https://ourworldindata.org/global-mental-health>

Needless to say, students will be longing for self-expression skills (Akat & Karatas, 2020). As the long period of irregularity will cause them sleeping difficulties and embarrassing feelings. The strength of the bonding of the relationship will be weakened and life satisfaction will be towards the same as well (Counseling Center, 2021). However, these won't show up without bringing some kind of positivity to the students. For instance- students will be abler to make proper use of technology (Mendler, 2021). Research demonstrates that learning has been

shown to increase retention of information, and will take less time than before which is going to impact them with positive psychological effects (Li & Lalani, 2020). Hard breakdown in the cognitive engagement may cause them afterward (Patricia Aguilera-Hermida, 2020).

4. SWOT Analysis of Post-psychological Impacts of COVID-19:

Due to the worldwide closure of all the education institutions, various virtual platforms has got structured and has been built just to recover the education gap by facilitating quality content. With the help of available MOOCs with proper interned using students can get immense assistance in learning in further, even after the COVID-19 period. Yet, the missing communication with friends, peers, and the teachers may cause them learning gap and some of the other communication essentials. There is a presence of immense probability that students will remain introvert, not having enough social skills. Additionally, long period of anomaly like: sleeping obliqueness which was resonated due to lengthy lockdown, may persist afterwards.

5. Colclusion: We realized that this Corona epidemic has affected us in many ways. Even in the field of education, this effect has become evident. Whose effect has not yet gone. Students are the future of the country and even after so much improvement in the field of education in this epidemic, the students did not get good results due to this monotony, moreover, they were mentally disturbed, many who are overly emotional have finally chosen the path of suicide.

Because they have suffered massive psychological problems while being held captive in the lockdown. That's why we need to pay special attention to the emotional problems of the students. Which is taking a long time to solve the problem. So we need to pay special attention to the emotional problems of the students. The advantages and disadvantages of studying online (study at home) are also discussed in detail here. And how these mental problems may increase in the aftermath of the epidemic is also discussed here. Also, after this epidemic, all kinds of discussions in the field of education and students have been briefly explained with strength, weakness, opportunity & threat analysis.

Authors' Contribution:

Farhana Binta Fozal has covered psychological effects on a student after COVID-19, online learning system, negative upshots on students' psychological health, being asocial might be a thing for later, learning wasn't ensured for all, mental health issues got raised, Distant Learning: future of education, psychological issues that may get found after COVID-19 & SWOT analysis of post-psychological impacts of COVID-19 section. Md Swaid Sameh has covered the abstract, introduction, objectives, methodology & limitations section. Tanvir Hasan Shuvo, Mir Jerine Farhath & Tanzim Hossain Oyshi have covered the conclusion section.

Acknowledgment:

All credit goes to our respected teachers: Kaji Asma Siddika, Assistant Professor, Govt. Bangla College, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Rawnak Jahan, Assistant Professor, Govt. Bangla College, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Tania Afroze, Assistant Professor, Govt. Bangla College, Dhaka, Bangladesh. Shamima Yeasmin, Lecturer, Govt. Bangla College, Dhaka, Bangladesh, & our beloved friends: Jannatul Ferdous Jeba, Undergraduate Student, Department of Mathematics, Jagannath University, Bangladesh, Mst. Nusrat Jahan, Undergraduate Student, Department of Economics, National University of Bangladesh.

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Cite this article:

Md Swaid Sameh, Farhana Binta Fozal, Tanvir Hasan Shuvo, Mir Jerine Farhath & Tanzim Hossain Oyshi (2022). Psychological Impact of Covid-19 Described With SWOT Analysis. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 7(1), 53-66. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5889747>

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